

BIGUANIDE SULPHATE AS A REAGENT FOR THE ESTIMATION OF NICKEL

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Nickel has been estimated volumetrically using biguanide sulphate which forms insoluble co-ordination compound with nickel.

Biguanide and its substitution products are known to form characteristic co-ordination compounds with bivalent metals like copper, nickel, cobalt, etc.*.

Rây and Saha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670), after a detailed study, have concluded that these compounds are of the type of inner-metallic complexes and thus account satisfactorily many of their properties such as strong colour, low solubility, etc.

Ray and Raychowdhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 149) used biguanide sulphate as a reagent for the estimation of copper. The present author finds that nickel also can be estimated volumetrically after precipitation as nickel biguanide hydroxide, which is practically insoluble in water specially in presence of alkali.

The method permits the separation of nickel from other metals such as beryllium, zinc, iron, aluminium, chromium, titanium, uranium, arsenic, antimony and bismuth in presence of alkaline tartrate.

Biguanide sulphate precipitates nickel in presence of alkali as a yellow silky precipitate of the composition $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{OH})_2$. It cannot be directly weighed as it loses weight during heating and absorbs carbon dioxide from air. Cobalt, copper, palladium, etc., which give complexes with the reagent in presence of alkali must be absent so also manganese, magnesium, cadmium, tin and silver which are precipitated as oxides. Anions, e.g., PO_4^{3-} , FeCy_6^{3-} , FeCy_6^{4-} etc. which give precipitate with Ni^{2+} ion and metals like calcium, barium, strontium and lead which give precipitate of sulphates should also be absent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Reagent Biguanide Sulphate.—It was prepared from dicyanodiamide and ammonium iodide according to the method described by Ostrogovich (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1910, II, 1890).

Procedure.—A nickel sulphate solution was prepared from Kahlbaum's reagent quality cobalt-free sample and standardised by means of dimethylglyoxime. To an acid solution, containing a known amount of nickel, was added an excess of 1% solution of the reagent biguanide sulphate (1 g. of biguanide sulphate in 100 c.c. water and made faintly ammoniacal). If the solution contains other elements such as chromium, beryllium, iron, aluminium, titanium, uranium, etc. a few grams of Rochelle salt, sufficient to hold these metals in solution, should be previously added. The solution was then cooled and then an excess of 2N caustic soda was added to it dropwise with stirring.

The nickel biguanide sulphate first precipitated changed with the excess of alkali into silky, yellow, crystalline precipitate of the base having the composition $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7)_2](\text{OH})_2$. A few c.c. more of caustic soda were added to the solution. In presence of zinc a large excess of alkali should be added to form zincate. The solution was then allowed to settle in the cold, filtered and washed with minimum quantity of cold water till free from alkali. The precipitate was then transferred by hot water and dissolved in a measured quantity of standard sulphuric acid and the excess acid was titrated at room temperature with standard alkali using Wesselow's indicator.

*Rathke (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 779); Emich (*Monatsch.*, 1883, 8, 395); Smolka and Friedrich (*ibid.*, 1888, 9, 277); Ziegelfauer (*ibid.*, 1896, 17, 648); Andreasch (*ibid.*, 1927, 48, 145); Ray and Bagch (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 18, 617).

The calculation is based on the following reaction:

$$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = \frac{\text{Ni}}{2} \text{ or 1 c.c. N-H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.0146725 \text{ g. of Ni.}$$

TABLE I

Ni (g.)	{	(taken, 0.01107 0.01107 0.01107 0.01549 0.01549 0.02214 0.02214 0.02214 0.02878 0.02878
		(found) 0.01102 0.01109 0.01108 0.01550 0.01558 0.02203 0.02211 0.02215 0.02865 0.02875

TABLE II

Separation of Ni from Al.			Separation of Ni from Fe.		
	Taken.	Found.		Taken.	Found.
Ni:	0.0201 g.	0.02014 g.	Ni:	0.0201 g.	0.02021
Al:	0.1843	—	Fe:	0.0510 g.	—
Ni:	0.0201	0.02014	Ni:	0.0201	0.02021
Al:	0.009215	—	Fe:	0.1020	—
Ni:	0.0201	0.02021	Ni:	0.03015	0.03028
Al:	0.009215	—	Fe:	0.0510	—
Ni:	0.0201	0.02006	Ni:	0.0201	0.02014
Al:	0.01843	—	Fe:	0.1020	—
Ni:	0.0201	0.02017	Separation of Ni from Be.		
Al:	0.05529	—	Ni:	0.0201	0.02021
Ni:	0.0201	0.02006	Be:	0.02	—
Al:	0.05529	—	Ni:	0.0201	0.02021
Separation of Ni from U.			Be:	0.01	—
Ni:	0.0201 g.	0.02008 g.	Ni:	0.0201	0.02014
U:	0.0227	—	Be:	0.04	—
Ni:	0.0201	0.02011	Separation of Ni from Ti.		
U:	0.0454	—	Ni:	0.0201	0.02008
Ni:	0.0201	0.02008	Ti:	0.0267	—
U:	0.0681	—	Ni:	0.0201	0.02015
Separation Ni from Zn.			Ti:	0.01335	—
Ni:	0.0201 g.	0.02014 g.	Ni:	0.0201	0.02015
Zn:	0.11	—	Ti:	0.0534	—
Ni:	0.0201	0.02021	Separation of Ni from Cr.		
Zn:	0.055	—	Ni:	0.0218 g.	0.02170 g.
Ni:	0.0201	0.02021	Cr:	0.009685	—
Zn:	0.11	—	Ni:	0.0218	0.02179
			Cr:	0.01977	—
			Ni:	0.0218	0.02177
			Cr:	0.03954	—

The method possesses certain advantages in that the reagent can be easily and cheaply prepared.

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